
INTERNAL GREEN MARKETING ORIENTATION AND ITS EFFECT ON COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE: EVIDENCE FROM AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

Discipline: Commerce

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Abstract

Environmental sustainability has recently risen to the top of the global political agenda and is now regarded as a key driver of innovation. The textile sector is the third-largest polluting industry, accounting for 10 percent of the world's greenhouse gas emissions. The worldwide use of apparel has increased to almost 62 million tonnes per year. As a result, when marketing their products, the textile industry must take sustainability into account. Unfortunately, the majority of companies still believe that using green marketing strategies will undermine their ability to compete. The current study investigated the effect of internal green marketing orientation (IGMO) on competitive advantage among retail textile companies in Kerala to unravel the relationship between green marketing strategy and competitiveness. The study's findings supported the view that a company's competitive advantage can be enhanced through internal green marketing initiatives.

Keywords : Internal green marketing orientation, Retail textile companies, Competitive advantage

Introduction

Climate change is now a major concern for all industries (Kumar et al., 2025). The state of the world's environment is in crisis. One of the main causes of all forms of pollution is industrial

(Papadas et al., 2019). The environment has been severely impacted by manufacturing and other business operations. A company is mindful of stakeholder pressure, customer sensitivity, and stricter rules for environmental preservation. As a result, corporate actions now need consideration of the environment (Viet, 2022). Organisations are forced to devise strategies for pollution control and natural resource preservation to address ecological challenges. However, many organisations still struggle to integrate sustainability into their operations. A green economy ensures competitive advantages to firms (Hasan & Ali, 2015). As a result, several organisations are implementing green business strategies to ensure long-term growth by incorporating green elements into their operations. Even though it is voluntary, an increasing number of organisations are pursuing this approach, and it has become a top priority and an important concern for businesses (Hasan & Ali, 2015). Recent scientific research depicts today's society's strong desire to behave sustainably towards the environment, their interest in economic and political contributions, and the social measures they adopt to minimise the impact of environmental issues (Martin & Schouten, 2012). Organisations can integrate sustainability into their activities by adopting green marketing practices with a holistic approach. Green marketing is defined as "the holistic management process responsible for identifying, anticipating and satisfying the requirements of customers and society, in a profitable and sustainable way" (Peattie, 1995). An organisation's holistic approach to the natural environment can be termed as green marketing orientation. The green marketing orientation is conceptualised as comprising three dimensions: strategic, tactical, and internal (Papadas et al., 2017). Long-term top-management activities and policies that focus on corporate environmental strategy, proactive environmental strategies, and external environmental stakeholders are referred to as strategic green marketing orientation (SGMO). Tactical Green Marketing Orientation (TGMO) entails taking short-term activities to change the standard marketing mix to one that is more environment friendly. Internal green marketing orientation (IGMO) entails the cross-pollination of environmental ideals throughout the firm to establish a more comprehensive corporate green culture (Papadas et al., 2017). Green Marketing is not only focused on promoting green products but also on marketing activities. This is because the whole aspect of marketing involves developing and sustaining customers (Selvakumar & Ramesh Pandi, 2016).

Customers in the 21st century are well aware of green products and interested in buying eco-friendly products. Since the retail industry has a close relationship with customers, they frequently use green techniques to improve business performance and customer loyalty. Green Marketing is one such marketing strategy that retailers have found to be more effective for capturing the entire market through customer satisfaction (Nautiyal, 2020). As we saw in the distribution channels of marketing, the retail sector plays a predominant role in the economy because it has direct contact with consumers. Hence the retail management should consider the term 'Sustainability' in their marketing. Retailers influence producers and consumers to adopt the green marketing concept (Martin

& Schouten, 2012). Green Marketing is prominent in the modern clothing and textile industry, as it is one of the world's most polluting sectors. The fast-fashion industry's disastrous business model has made the synthetic materials produced from fossil fuels indispensable to the fashion sector. Cheap synthetic fibres, the mainstay of the fast-fashion business model driven by excessive consumption and overproduction, have serious environmental consequences throughout their lifecycle, from production to disposal.

By adopting the green marketing concept, the clothing and textile industry designs eco-friendly clothing and textile products and processes, promotes eco-friendly communication tools, and distributes them. Hence, it will not harm the environment (Vandana Tripathi Nautiyal, 2020). Even though prior studies focused on internal green marketing orientation, none of them addressed internal green marketing orientation in retail textile companies. The industry should concentrate on corporate environmental ethics alongside its ultimate goal of profit maximisation when marketing its products. While adopting green marketing practices, the industry gains opportunities such as profit maximisation, social responsibility, minimising governmental pressure, gaining a competitive advantage, and cost reduction (Mourad and Ahmed, 2012). There is limited evidence that proactive environmental practices could improve firms' competitive advantage in developing countries. Hence, the present study focuses on the internal green marketing orientation aspect of the holistic green marketing approach and analyses its effect on competitive advantage in retail textile companies.

Objectives

1. To assess the level of adoption of internal green marketing orientation in retail textile companies.
2. To analyse the effect of internal green marketing orientation on competitive advantage for retail textile companies.

Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Proactive environmental management practices include strategic green marketing orientation (SGMO), tactical green marketing orientation (TGMO), and internal green marketing orientation (IGMO) (Borah et al., 2022). The term green marketing orientation (GMO) was coined to describe a firm's holistic orientation toward the natural environment (Papadas et al., 2017). From an internally driven perspective, environmentally proactive companies may adopt an internal green marketing orientation (Papadas et al., 2019). Internal green marketing orientation entails the cross-pollination of environmental ideals throughout the firm to establish a more comprehensive corporate green culture (Papadas et al., 2017). Internal green marketing orientation includes: Communicating and resolving significant environmental concerns, establishing environmental programs and policies, rewarding personnel for environmental improvements, and allocating organisational resources to environmental efforts (Papadas et al., 2019). There is a need for an internal green marketing strategy

that more responsibly balances growth goals with sustainability, connects behaviors with values, and fosters an ethical corporate culture (Kotler et al., 2011). According to the resource-based view (RBV), a stronger corporate culture is one of the most important resources for generating sustainable competitive advantage (J. B. Barney, 1986). A superior corporate culture can be practiced by the organisation via adopting an internal green marketing orientation. Internal green marketing-oriented practices allow the company to use resources effectively. Hence, studying the association between internal green marketing orientation and competitive advantage is essential. No studies addressed internal green marketing orientation in relation to competitive advantage. This study fills the research gap by investigating the association between internal green marketing orientation and competitive advantage.

Hypothesis Formulation

A company's competitive advantage is derived from its key resources and competencies. Environmental social responsibility, according to RBV, may become a significant competency that contributes to a sustained competitive advantage. Environmental dynamics, such as environmental rules and regulations, competition, stakeholder pressure, and environmentalism, all affect how businesses operate. Businesses must practice environmental management to comply with environmental legislation and consumer environmental concerns. As a result, green marketing practices may be a significant part of a company's strategy, and it is viewed as a separate competence in the RBV logic (Chang, 2011).

Internal green marketing orientation (IGMO) entails the cross-pollination of environmental ideals throughout the firm to establish a more comprehensive green culture. Employee training aims to raise environmental consciousness within the business, and environmental leadership activities are examples of such efforts (Papadas et al., 2017). Employees may build the skills and capacity to implement successful environmental initiatives by disseminating knowledge and integrating an environmental culture throughout the company (McDonagh & Prothero, 2014). Environmental awareness education and training for the entire organisation may also help to develop environmental champions. Discussing and resolving important environmental issues, initiating environmental programs, rewarding staff members for environmental activities, and allocating organizational resources to environmental projects, etc., are major initiatives of environmentally proactive organizations (Papadas et al., 2017). Internal green initiatives help the management team engage every employee in green actions and reap the benefits of these efforts, such as higher revenues from lower expenses. This implementation encourages operations to use resources efficiently and reduce waste, allowing marketers to differentiate themselves by enhancing their company's reputation (Papadas et al., 2019). In the modern economy, intangible assets have become a critical determinant of a company's competitive advantage (Chen, 2008). Companies' human capital has a favourable impact on their

competitive advantages (Johnson, 1999). The employee's knowledge, skills, capabilities, experience, attitudes, wisdom, creativity, commitments, etc., regarding environmental protection or green innovation can help companies gain competitive advantages (Chen, 2008). These studies indicate the potential effect of internal green marketing orientation on competitive advantage, leading to the development of the research hypothesis that internal green marketing orientations have a significant positive effect on competitive advantage.

Methodology and Measurement

Data Collection and the Sample

The study is descriptive and analytical, based on primary data collected through a structured questionnaire. Textile companies in Kerala constituted the study population, and managers were the respondents. 'city.webindia.com' provided the sampling frame, comprising 117 companies. A sample of 90 companies was randomly selected, and of these, 72 valid questionnaires were received back, yielding an overall response rate of 80 percent.

Measures

To assess the constructs, a 5-point Likert scale (1-5), ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree, was used. The seven-item scale by Papadas et al. (2017) was used to measure internal green marketing orientation (IGMO). The five-item scale developed by Vaitone et al. (2022) was used to measure the level of adoption of internal green marketing orientation (IGMO). Competitive advantage was measured with six items developed by Barney (1991).

Internal Green Marketing Orientation

The seven items scale was used to measure internal green marketing orientation (IGMO). 1) Exemplar environmental behaviour is acknowledged and rewarded. 2) Environmental activities by candidates are a bonus in our recruitment process. 3) We have created internal environmental prize competitions that promote eco-friendly behaviour, 4) We form environmental committees for implementing internal audits of environmental performance, 5.) We organize presentations for our employees to inform them about our green marketing strategy, 6) We encourage our employees to use eco-friendly products/services, and 7) Our employees believe in the environmental values of our organization (Papadas et al., 2017).

Level of Adoption of Internal Green Marketing Orientation

The level of adoption of internal green marketing orientation was measured with five items. Items for measurement include 1) Environmental issues are very relevant to the major functioning of the company 2) Our company has a clear policy statement that calls for environmental awareness in

all areas of operation 3) We try to promote environmental preservation as a major goal across all departments 4) At our company we make a concerted effort to make every employee understand the importance of environmental preservations 5) We apply the paperless policy in our personnel management where possible (Vaitone et al., 2022).

Competitive Advantage

Competitive advantage was measured with six items and items include 1) the quality of the products or services that the company offers is better than that of the competitor's products or services; (2) the company is more capable of R&D than the competitors; (3) the company has better managerial capability than the competitors; (4) the company's profitability is better; (5) the corporate image of the company is better than that of the competitors; and (6) the competitors are difficult to take the place of the company's competitive advantage (Barney, 1991)

Results

Table I

The Cronbach's alpha coefficients of the constructs

Constructs	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha	Remark
Internal green marketing orientation	7	0.884	Acceptable
Competitive advantage	6	0.899	Acceptable
Level of adoption of internal green marketing practices	5	0.808	Acceptable

Source: Primary Survey Data

Table II

Descriptive Statistics

Constructs	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min.	Max.
Level of adoption	2.3972	.45963	1.20	3.00
Competitive advantage	4.2106	1.23302	3.00	13.17
Internal green marketing orientation	3.6865	.55543	2.57	4.71

Source: Primary Survey Data

The Cronbach's alpha coefficients of the constructs were shown in Table I. The coefficient of reliability is used as a measure of internal consistency or reliability. A value greater than .7 is

widely considered a good score. Of the three aspects measured, all have a value beyond this threshold limit, indicating higher reliability of the measurement scales adopted. Table II shows the descriptive statistics of the study.

Table III

Mean Score Analysis

Item	Min.	Max.	Mean	Mean Score Analysis
Level of adoption	1.20	3.00	2.3972	79.90%

Source: Primary Survey Data

Table III showed the level of adoption of internal green marketing practices in retail textile companies. If the value of the mean score is greater than 75%, it is in a highly agreed-upon area. The result shows that the mean score is 79.90% and this means that retail trading textile companies are highly practicing internal green marketing activities.

Table IV

Empirical Results of Regression analysis

Dependent variable: Competitive advantage

Independent variable

Internal green marketing orientation	$p < .001 (1.01e-06^{***})$
R- Squared	0.291011
Adjusted R-squared	0.280882
N	72
F	28.73209

Table IV is the results of the regression analysis. It is apparent from the table that internal green marketing orientation has a positive effect on the competitive advantage of the firms. It can be inferred that more investments in internal green marketing-orientated activities can enhance the competitive advantage.

Conclusion

Globally, environmental protection is a critical issue (Alhosseini Almodarresi et al., 2019). Green marketing is a strategy that improves the well-being of the company and society (Mi et al., 2020). Environmentally conscious consumers are more likely to use eco-friendly products . IGMO

is a term used to describe a set of organizational initiatives that are intended to promote environmental values across the organisation and create a more comprehensive culture of environmental awareness (Elshaer et al., 2024). These actions include encouraging employees to use eco-friendly goods and services, increasing staff members' understanding of environmental issues, and integrating employees' environmental initiatives into hiring and promotion procedures (Papadas et al., 2019). IGM's activities foster a supportive organizational culture (Elshaer et al., 2024). The study assessed the level of adoption of internal green marketing orientation activities and their effect on competitive advantage. The results reveal that retail textile companies engage in extensive internal green marketing, and that these activities positively affect competitive advantage.

Discussion and Implications

There is no alternative to sustainable growth; however, most businesses continue to believe that adopting more environmentally friendly practices would undermine their competitiveness. This slows development and creates a fragmented understanding of environmental issues in marketing. Organisation efficiency and effectiveness can be enhanced by a proactive environmental strategy (Russo & Fouts, 1997). Developing nations can become more competitive in the international market by adopting a proactive environmental strategy (Ko et al., 2021).

Proactive environmental management practices include strategic green marketing orientation (SGMO), tactical green marketing orientation (TGMO), and internal green marketing orientation (IGMO) (Borah et al., 2022; Papadas et al., 2017). There is a need for a redefined, greener marketing strategy that more responsibly balances growth goals with sustainability, connects behaviours with values, and fosters an ethical corporate culture. One of the key elements of organisational culture is corporate environmental ethics, which formalises corporate values. So, it is a major force for competitive advantage. The empirical results of this study showed that internal green marketing-oriented practices can enhance competitive advantage. Recruiting candidates who have actively participated in environmental activities, recognising and rewarding ideal environmental behaviour, fostering eco-friendly behaviour through internal environmental prize competitions, organising environmental awareness programmes for employees, and encouraging employees to use eco-friendly products or services may assist the business in developing superior managerial competencies and creating a distinctive culture that distinguishes it from competitors.

Even though the study's results confirm that internal green marketing orientation practices can enhance units' competitiveness, the strength of this relationship may also be moderated by other variables. The adoption of green practices may be influenced by a company's size, as larger businesses face greater environmental pressure and have greater access to resources than smaller businesses (Vanpoucke et al., 2014). Larger units can more successfully adopt internal green initiatives and

turn them into competitive advantages, as they often have greater technological and financial resources. During periods of economic uncertainty, units may not prioritize internal green marketing orientation initiatives; instead, they may focus on reducing expenses to ensure financial stability. But during periods of economic volatility, regulatory pressure may increase to adopt a green orientation. So, the influence of internal green marketing-oriented practices on competitive advantage is context-dependent and can be moderated by internal and external factors.

The rising cost of sustainable materials poses a challenge for the units as they adopt a green marketing orientation. Hence, the units should reduce waste, pursue energy optimization, and prioritize green innovation. The units should consider adopting a green marketing orientation as a long-term strategic decision. Circular economy practices, such as reuse and recycling, to a great extent reduce dependence on expensive materials.

The study's findings could provide insights for other developing nations and the retail industry. Kerala is an example of an emerging market with environmentally conscious consumers demanding sustainable products. These circumstances are also more prevalent in many developing economies. The majority of units today are reluctant to adopt green practices due to resource constraints, cost pressures, and the need to balance sustainability and profitability. According to current research, an internal green marketing orientation can be an effective tool for overcoming these obstacles and gaining a competitive edge. To improve their market positioning, companies in other emerging regions could implement internal sustainability practices. A unit that prioritizes sustainability can find ways to overcome challenges to the adoption of green practices. Hence, it is essential to ensure that the units adopt internal green marketing practices.

Limitations and future research directions

The data is collected only from textile companies, so the results cannot be generalized to other sectors. Geographical limitations are also a concern, as the data is collected only from the state of Kerala. Although the study's results make a valuable contribution to the literature, the small sample size is also a limitation.

Future research should focus on strategic and tactical components of green marketing orientation and how they could enhance competitive advantage. Other sectors should also be considered in future studies to determine whether the results are similar across industries. Furthermore, moderating variables, such as firm size, should also be considered in future investigations.

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